

COMPARATIVE STUDY OF RUSSIAN AND ENGLISH PUBLIC SPEECHES

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Annotation: This thesis explores the cultural and linguistic features of public speaking in Russian and English. It examines how Russian speakers often emphasize emotional appeal and collectivist values, while English speakers tend to prioritize clarity, logic, and individual expression. Through the analysis of public speeches, the study highlights how each language reflects its cultural identity and rhetorical traditions in spoken discourse.

Keywords: public speeches, collectivism, emotional appeal, metaphors, historical and cultural symbols, stylistic devices.

Аннотация: В данной работе исследуются культурные и языковые особенности публичной речи на русском и английском языках. В исследовании рассматривается, как русскоязычные ораторы чаще делают акцент на эмоциональную выразительность и коллективные ценности, тогда как англоязычные предпочитают ясность, логику и индивидуальное самовыражение. Анализируя примеры публичных выступлений, исследование подчеркивает, как каждая языковая традиция отражает свою культурную идентичность и риторические особенности в устной речи.

Ключевые слова: публичные выступления, коллективизм, эмоциональный призыв, метафоры, исторические и культурные символы, стилистические средства.

Most of the public speeches and printed public works that are intended for a large audience and focused on significant social or political events, as well as public issues of cultural or moral nature, are employed by the publicistic style. There are three types of it, and each has unique characteristics. The publicistic style, particularly the oratorical sub-style, features spoken variations in contrast to other formal styles [3; 288.]. Persuasion is the main goal of oratory which is achieved through eloquence [1; 72.]. Speeches on contemporary social and contemporary issues, orations and addresses at solemn events such as speeches of court judges, political campaigns, weddings and debates are all examples of oratory. Crucial topics in fields like science, art, or business interactions are rarely discussed since the use of oratory is limited to appealing to an audience. A new spoken variety known as radio and television

commentary has emerged as a result of the advancements in these media. The essays and magazine, journal, and newspaper articles make up the other two [2]. The publicistic style's primary objective is to sway public opinion by persuading the reader or listener that the writer's or speaker's interpretation is the only accurate one and encouraging him to accept the viewpoint presented in the speech, essay, or article, and not just through logical arguments, but also through emotional appeals. Publicistic writing is distinguished by its combination of persuasive and informative language, frequently using stylistic devices to effectively engage readers and communicate difficult concepts. This thesis explores the differences and similarities in how stylistic devices are used in Russian and English publicistic writing. It focuses on analyzing their role in creating emphasis, appeal, and emotional resonance [6; 4.].

The historical legacy of publicistic writing in Russian is based on the writings of authors such as Maxim Gorky and Alexander Herzen, who employed publicistic writing to encourage social reform. In English, it has been influenced by writers like George Orwell and Thomas Paine, who placed an emphasis on logic and clarity in addition to rhetorical flair. The conditions of communication dictate the stylistic devices used in the public speeches, newspaper and journalistic articles. For instance, the speaker will employ a number of conventional stylistic elements if he wants to arouse and maintain the audience's interest such as an antithesis framed by parallel constructions, which, in their turn, are accompanied by repetition, while a climax can be formed by repetitions of different kinds [3; 208.]. In the Gettysburg Address by A. Lincoln, we can observe the usage of this combination: “But, in a larger sense, *we cannot dedicate – we cannot consecrate – we cannot hallow this ground.... It is for us the living, rather, to be dedicated here to the unfinished work which they who fought here have thus far so nobly advanced. It is rather for us to be dedicated to the great task remaining before us – that from these honoured dead we take increased devotion to that cause for which they gave the last full measure of devotion – that we here highly resolve that these dead shall not have died in vain – that this nation, under God, shall have a new birth of freedom – and that the government of the people, by the people, for the people, shall not perish from the earth*” [2].

Collectivism and shared history are highly valued in Russian culture. This is evident in publicistic writing's frequent use of rhetorical questions, historical metaphors, and emotional appeals. In V. Lenin's Red Army Address, we can notice how he engaged the audience emotionally, appealing to their shared experiences of suffering and reflecting collectivist ideals: “*Красная Армия непобедима, ибо она объединила миллионы трудовых крестьян с рабочими, которые научились теперь бороться,*

научились товарищеской дисциплине, не падают духом, закаляются после небольших поражений, ...Товарищи красноармейцы! *Стойте крепко, стойко, дружно!* Смело вперёд против врага! За нами будет победа. Власть помещиков и капиталистов, сломленная в России, будет побеждена во всем мире!" [7]. Because of its rich vocabulary and inflectional structure, the Russian language enables writers to create more complex structures and integration of stylistic devices. English publications, particularly from news outlets such as The Guardian or The New York Times, prefer understatement and irony, reflecting Anglo-American traditions of subtlety. Alliteration and concise metaphors are prominent, providing an appealing yet reserved tone. Covering abstract political processes and decisions is not the only application of embodied metaphors as well as widely recognized image schemata [4; 49.]. Indeed, scientific reports of new findings and technologies also benefit greatly from its use. For instance, "How the brain starts *going downhill* at 45: Scientists find mental *decline sets in* much earlier than they had thought: British men and women suffer the same 3.6 per cent *loss* between the ages of 45–49. Whilst older men aged 65–70 *fare* worse with a 9.6 per cent *drop* in comparison with the 7.4 for their female counterparts." The usage of negative verb and noun phrases such as "going downhill", "decline sets in", "fare" or "drop" intensifies the effect of visualization of gradual brain "loss" and by being backed up with the strategy of using numbers and percentage figures it highlights credibility of the information [5; 160.]. Meanwhile in Russian publicism, to ensure key ideas are memorable and create rhythm and cohesion in the speech and text, they used repetition. In V. Lenin's speech "How to save the workers from the oppression of landlords and capitalists", we can notice the emphasis on collectivism with the usage of repetition: "...рабочие и крестьяне не смогут прожить *без нас. Без нас* некому будет установить порядка, распределить работу, принудить к труду. *Без нас* всё развалится, и государство распадётся..." [7]. Additionally, in English publicism, repetition is used to support the speaker's position and persuade the listener. In the following extract from the speech of the American Confederate general, A.P. Hill, on the ending of the Civil War in the U.S.A., we can clearly observe the application of anaphoric repetition: "*It is high time* this people had recovered from the passions of war. *It is high time* that counsel were taken from statesmen, not demagogues... *It is high time* the people of the North and South understood each other and adopted means to inspire confidence in each other" [2].

To sum up, in order to inspire a sense of unity and shared purpose, Russian publicistic literature frequently uses historical and cultural symbols in an emotive and collectivist manner. In Russian publications, stylistic devices like metaphors and

repetitions can heighten emotional resonance and motivate group action. On the other hand, English public speeches place more emphasis on individual expression, logic, and clarity. Persuasive arguments frequently prioritize reason over sentimentality. Although the stylistic devices have similar uses, the comparative study shows that their use conforms to the corresponding linguistic and cultural standards. This emphasizes how language and culture interact to shape publicistic writing, which is a crucial instrument for analyzing and shaping public opinion.

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